

The Future of Dining: Investigating the Effects of Robotics on Customer Service Efficiency in Selected Metro Manila Food Service Establishments

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of robotics on customer service efficiency in Metro Manila food service establishments. Specifically, it tested the mediating roles of Speed of Service and Task Consistency, and the moderating influence of generational cohorts on these relationships. A quantitative study using a descriptive-correlational approach was employed. The data were collected from 400 diners/customers of selected food service establishments in Metro Manila that utilize robots, selected via Convenience sampling. Respondents were segmented into four generational cohorts such as Gen Z, Gen Y/Millennials, Gen X, and Baby Boomers. The data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The structural model revealed that the use of robotics has a significant but weak positive effect on customer service efficiency. Robotics also showed a significant, moderate influence on both Speed of Service and Task Consistency. In the mediation analysis, Task Consistency resulted as a significant positive mediator and predictor of efficiency, while speed of service was found to be non-significant. In the moderation analysis, the effects of generational cohorts such as Gen Z and Gen Y on the robotics-efficiency link were found to be non-significant. The study concludes that the strategic value of robotics in food service establishments is achieved primarily by enhancing Task Consistency and Reliability, which customers prioritize over speed alone.

Keywords: Robotics, Service Robots, Task Consistency, Customer Service Efficiency, Speed of Service, Food Service Establishments

INTRODUCTION

In an age where technology continues to redefine everyday experiences, the integration of robotics into the food and beverage sector presents an intriguing evolution in the dynamics of customer service. The integration of robotics within the food service industry is rapidly transforming conventional operational paradigms, presenting substantial opportunities for enhancing customer service efficiency (Tuomi et al., 2020). Studies suggest that having robotic systems in restaurants builds up operational efficiency, streamlines service delivery, and substantially reduces wait times, resulting in a higher quality of customer experience (Kumar et al., 2021). This paradigm shift is particularly evident in high-contact service sectors like restaurants, where artificial intelligence and robotics are increasingly being deployed to automate operations and revolutionize guest interactions, albeit still in their nascent stages (Blöcher & Alt, 2020).

As global trends highlight the rising implementation of robotics for enhanced customer service efficiency, as evidenced by studies on consumer acceptance, human-robot interactions, and consumer innovativeness in robotic restaurants (Gursoy et al., 2019; Moriuchi & Murdy, 2024; Hwang et al., 2020), in Philippine food service

establishments, its implementation, particularly in Metro Manila, presents a different scenario. Existing studies have emphasized the role of human–robot interaction in hospitality, highlighting factors such as perceived value and the sharing of empathic information that shape customers’ willingness to engage with social robots (De Kervenoael et al., 2019). Furthermore, case studies, such as the Henn na Cafe in Japan, show the current condition of AI-powered human-robot relationships in customer service (Reis, 2024). Alejandro et al. (2025) also note the rise of service robots in selected quick-service restaurants in the Philippines and assess the impact on customer experience and satisfaction. Yet, the direct effects of this technology on customer service efficiency in this specific context are lacking in-depth research. These results suggest that integrating robotics in food service establishments in Metro Manila, as well as their particular effects on customer service efficiency, warrant further investigation within the local context.

This study aims to investigate the impact of robotics on customer service efficiency in selected food service establishments in Metro Manila. Specifically, it explores how these technologies influence key service dimensions such as speed and task consistency. This topic is timely and relevant as technological innovations continue to reshape the food service industry. Food Service Establishments in Metro Manila, which are the hubs of consumer activity and urban development, are beginning to adopt these advancements to improve service delivery. Although global studies have explored the effects of robotics on customer satisfaction, much of this research has been concentrated in Western and other Asian contexts. As Alejandro et al. (2025) noted, the Philippine market presents a unique socio-cultural and economic landscape where consumer expectations and technological acceptance may differ. Understanding how Filipino customers perceive and respond to service robots is crucial to filling this contextual research gap. The results of this research can provide valuable guidance to restaurant managers, business owners, and hospitality professionals seeking to enhance service efficiency through technological innovation.

Furthermore, individuals intending to become business owners may also benefit from this research, as it will help them determine whether incorporating robotics into the food service establishment they plan to operate will be advantageous. Entrepreneurs globally can benefit from our research, as it provides updates on the status of robotics in food service establishments in Metro Manila. Additionally, educators, especially those in the hospitality and business industries, can benefit from this research by staying updated and creating new strategies, training modules, or development programs to help individuals prepare their businesses for a technologically driven foodservice landscape. Ultimately, this study seeks to provide a deeper understanding of how robotics influences customer service efficiency in the Philippine context, thereby informing decisions that strike a balance between technological adoption and the Filipino brand of hospitality.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Use of Robotics in the Food Service Establishments

In the food service industry, robotics refers to the use of autonomous, programmable machines, also called service robots, that carry out operational tasks traditionally performed by human staff, such as ordering, cooking, and delivering to customers (Hwang et al., 2020). While many studies emphasize customer-facing robots that interact and communicate directly with diners, robotics in food service also includes operational models designed mainly for support functions, such as food delivery, table bussing, and kitchen operations. These robots are now common in both front-of-house and back-of-house work. Examples include serving robots that bring food to tables, robotic arms used in cooking, and tray-return or bussing robots (Alt, 2021; Ivanov & Webster, 2019). In some cases, robotics is used to deliver specialized services, such as robotic baristas that prepare coffee with precise and repeatable brewing methods, ensuring consistent flavor and quality across multiple servings. This feature not only enhances customer satisfaction but also strengthens brand reputation in commercial settings (Park et al., 2023). Moreover, El-Said and Hajri (2022) found that customers reported high satisfaction with robotic service during the COVID-19 pandemic, because of improved hygiene, efficiency, and service reliability as significant advantages. In addition, robots help

reduce wait times and increase operational speed, especially when performing repetitive tasks, and quick-service restaurants using service robots reported higher customer-perceived service speed (Ivanov & Webster, 2019; Alejandro et al., 2025). While some studies note that the lack of human interaction may reduce the perceived warmth of service (Wirtz et al., 2021), the improvements in consistency, accuracy, and overall efficiency remain valuable contributions to modern food service establishment operations.

Speed of Service

One of the most critical components of the overall customer experience, aside from food quality, is the speed of service. Speed of service covers the time from when an order is placed to when the food is served and payment is completed, to keep wait times as short as possible. El-Said and Hajri (2022) found that the speed of service has a significant and positive effect on guest satisfaction during the COVID-19 pandemic. Service robots can enhance the customer experience by streamlining processes and making services more convenient (Zemke et al., 2025). In quick-service restaurants (QSRs), Alejandro et al. (2025) noted that speed of service is perceived as the timely and efficient delivery of services, particularly when enhanced through the use of robotic systems. Establishments that use serving robots or robotic tray-return can handle operations more efficiently and serve customers faster. In addition, robots also contribute to contactless service by delivering meals directly to tables without human staff interaction, a feature that became especially valuable during health-conscious periods like the pandemic. For instance, the first store of Genki Sushi in Bandung, Indonesia, the “Kousoku Lane” system uses a double-decker high-speed track, which is twice as fast as a traditional conveyor belt, to deliver orders directly to diners, integrating both ordering and delivery functions for a faster and more unique service experience (Janice et al., 2023). According to studies by El-Said and Hajri (2022) and Santiago et al. (2024), food service establishments that utilize robotic systems have shown improvements in service speed, operational efficiency, and overall customer satisfaction, with customers perceiving robotic services as fast, reliable, and hygienic.

Task Consistency

In Metro Manila’s food service industry, one significant advantage of robotics is its ability to perform food preparation and service tasks with a high level of consistency. This consistency means the same standards are met every time, which can help enhance customer satisfaction and build brand loyalty (Wirtz et al., 2018). Robotic technologies such as robotic chefs, automated kitchen systems, and robot servers help remove variations caused by human factors. They do this by standardizing tasks such as ingredient handling, the precision of cooking, and the service of tables (Ivanov & Webster, 2019; Parvez, 2025). Customers tend to trust this level of predictability, which encourages them to come back, especially when compared to human service, which can be affected by things like fatigue, stress, or mood changes (Alejandro et al., 2025; Alt, 2021). Zemke et al. (2025) also emphasized that service robots reduce common mistakes and deliver steady performance, improving order accuracy and making the dining experience more uniform. Although the cost of these systems can be high, Shinde et al. (2025) argue that over time, the benefits, such as fewer errors, higher efficiency, and more dependable service, can outweigh the expense.

Customer Service Efficiency

Customer service is a significant factor in the success of any food establishment because it affects how people perceive the quality of the place, their level of satisfaction, and brand loyalty (Dinero & Apritado, 2021). Customers in today’s competitive dining market want not only great food but also smooth and efficient service (Li & Adam, 2021). The integration of robotics into food service operations is a promising opportunity to improve customer service efficiency. Robotic systems, such as food-serving robots, robotic tray return systems, and kitchen automation machines, can help speed up regular tasks, reduce errors, and make the workflow smoother. According to Samaniego et al. (2024), the presence of robots in food service establishments resulted in better operational flow and more consistent service, which in turn created a more enjoyable experience and encouraged repeat visits. By reducing service delays and improving order accuracy, robotics can enhance both customer satisfaction and reliability. They also keep service steady during busy times, which customers often see as a sign of efficiency and dependability (El-Said & Hajri, 2022). As robotic systems perform tasks with precision and consistency, they

directly contribute to improved service efficiency, allowing food service establishment staff to focus more on complex customer needs or interpersonal service elements.

Generational Cohorts as a Moderating Variable

Robotics in food service can offer numerous benefits, but it's worth noting that people of different generations don't always respond to them in the same way. Other age groups may perceive and react to service robots differently. Younger customers, who often have more experience with technology, are generally more open to robot-assisted service and may even see it as a sign of modern convenience and speed (Okafuji et al., 2022). Older customers, however, may be more at ease with traditional service and sometimes find robotic interactions distant or hard to follow. Asrifan et al. (2025) observed that attitudes range from cautious to enthusiastic, with older groups tending to be more hesitant, while Millennials and Gen Z are more curious and accepting due to their digital upbringing and frequent exposure to emerging technologies. These generational differences can shape how service robots are received and influence overall satisfaction with technology-driven service. As Cheong and Law (2023) suggest, businesses could bridge the gap by tailoring their approach to meet the preferences of diverse age groups; for instance, using robots to handle efficiency-focused tasks but keeping human staff available to maintain a personal touch for those who prefer it.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework on the Impact of Robotics on Customer Service Efficiency

H1: The use of robotics in selected Metro Manila food service establishments has a significant positive effect on customer service efficiency.

H2: The use of robotics in selected Metro Manila food service establishments has a significant positive effect on the speed of service.

H2a: Speed of service has a significant positive effect on perceived customer service efficiency.

H2b: Speed of service significantly mediates the relationship between the use and significance of robotics and customer service efficiency.

H3: The use of robotics in selected Metro Manila food service establishments has a significant positive effect on task consistency.

H3a: Task consistency has a significant positive effect on customer service efficiency.

H3b: Task consistency significantly mediates the relationship between the use and significance of robotics and customer service efficiency.

H4: The customer's generational cohorts moderate the relationship between the use of robotics in selected Metro Manila food service establishments and customer service efficiency.

METHODS

This study aims to fill the gap using a quantitative research approach to collect, analyze, and interpret data. Specifically, it uses a descriptive-correlational approach to describe variables such as customer service efficiency and to examine the relationships between these variables and the use of robotics in food service establishments. As Alejandro et al. (2025) explain, descriptive analysis systematically portrays a population or phenomenon, while correlational analysis identifies associations between variables. This design is appropriate for investigating the effects of robotics on customer service efficiency in selected food service establishments in Metro Manila. The respondents in this study were customers who visited and dined at the selected food service establishments that utilize robotics, such as the following:

Table 1. List of Metro Manila Food Service Establishments that Use Robotics

FOOD SERVICE ESTABLISHMENT	LOCATION	TYPE	TYPE OF ROBOTICS
Dunkin	733 Aurora Blvd, Quezon City, 1112 Metro Manila Eastwood Citywalk 1, E. Rodriguez Ave. (C-5), Bagumbayan, Libis, Quezon City, Metro Manila Upper Ground Level of SM City North Edsa 1139 Epifanio de los Santos Ave, Project 7, Quezon City, 1105 Metro Manila	Quick-Service Restaurant	Robotic Server
Ella The Robot Barista	Mezzanine Floor, Clipp Center, 11th Avenue corner 39th Street, BGC, Taguig City Level 2, Mega A SM Megamall, Ortigas Center, Mandaluyong City	Smart Cafe	Robot Barista
Genki Sushi	28 General Araneta, Cubao, Quezon City, 1109 Metro Manila SM Aura Premier, Lower Ground, 8 McKinley Pkwy, Taguig City, Metro Manila	Fast-Casual Dining Restaurant	Bullet Train Robotic Server / Conveyor Belt
Jollibee	GF SM Aura Premier, 26th St, cor McKinley Pkwy, Taguig City, Metro Manila U.P. Town Center, Level 1, Katipunan Ave, Quezon City, Metro Manila	Quick-Service Restaurant	Robotic Server
Oedo Japanese Restaurant	105 Sto. Domingo Avenue, Corner Scout Oscar M. Alcaraz St, Quezon City, Metro Manila	Fast-Casual Dining Restaurant	Robotic Server

SM Aura Premier Food Court	4th floor, SM Aura Premier, at the corner of 26th Street, Taguig City, Metro Manila	Food Court (QSR)	Bussing Robot / Clearing Robot
SM Mall of Asia Food Hall	1300 Ocean Dr, Pasay City, Metro Manila	Food Court (QSR)	Bussing Robot / Clearing Robot
Tokyo Grill Unlimited Japanese Restaurant	62 Tomas Morato Ave, Quezon City, 1112 Metro Manila	Fast-Casual Dining Restaurant	Robotic Server

All of the selected food service establishments are within Metro Manila. Respondents who had visited other food service establishments beyond the initially identified locations were also included in the study, provided that these establishments utilized robotics. The respondents were customers aged 18 years and above, of any gender, who voluntarily consented to participate in the survey until the required sample size was achieved. They will be recruited from selected food service establishments in Metro Manila that use robotics, as well as through online platforms such as Facebook and Messenger. The minimum required sample size was determined using power analysis. The analysis indicated that a sample size of 122 would be sufficient to detect a small effect size (minimum R^2 as low as 10%) with 80% power and a 0.05 significance level. However, to ensure a higher probability of detecting effects and to improve the overall quality of the results, a more robust sample size was chosen, which is set at 400 respondents. This larger sample size is expected to provide greater statistical power and more reliable outcomes. This sample will be selected through convenience sampling to ensure accessibility and relevance to the study and will utilize a survey questionnaire to achieve the main objective. Researchers prepared questionnaires that incorporated dichotomous questions and a 7-point Likert Scale. The questionnaire was structured to gather necessary information for each construct, which comprises of eight (8) sections: an introduction providing research context and confidentiality assurances, screener questions to filter relevant participants, and a demographics section identifying moderators like generation. The questionnaire also assessed the Use of Robotics (adapted from Chi et al., 2021), Speed of Service (adapted from El-Said et al., 2022, and Santiago et al., 2023), and Task Consistency (adapted from Chi et al., 2021). Customer service efficiency, with two (2) sub-parts of it, such as tangibles and empathy, was evaluated using a self-administered questionnaire based on the SERVPERF model (Cronin & Taylor, 1992, 1994), tailored to robotics-driven service in QSR and Fast-Casual Dining sectors. The SERVPERF model was selected for its focus on customer perceptions of service performance. This section included 11 items across two dimensions of perceived service performance, measured on a 7-point Likert scale to capture nuances in respondent perceptions of robot customer service efficiency. Some questions included in the survey questionnaire are also adapted from El-Said et al. (2022), who adapted questions from TAM Models (e.g., Davis 1989; Davis et al., 1992) and subsequent research that concentrates on service robots (e.g., Lu et al., 2019; Hwang et al., 2020). The primary tool used in the study is a combination of online and hard-copy survey questionnaires. An online survey questionnaire was used for online respondents, while a hard-copy survey questionnaire was used for respondents in the location. Before answering the survey, face-to-face respondents will be provided with informed consent forms. Meanwhile, online survey questionnaires will be distributed to participants recruited through social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Messenger. All responses will be tallied, tabulated, and analyzed for interpretation upon completion and will be collected from both online and in-person surveys, which will be checked, coded, and compiled into a single database to prepare the data for analysis. After organizing the dataset, descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, weighted means, and standard deviations will be calculated. These measures will be used to summarize the demographic profile of the respondents and to provide an initial view of the major variables related to customer service efficiency and the use of robotics in food service establishments. The main statistical technique used for testing the study's hypotheses was Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). This approach was selected because it is the most suitable for examining predictive relationships and for analyzing complex models. Prior to examining the structural paths, the measurement model was evaluated. Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability were used to assess the Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for the

Convergent Validity. Moreover, Discriminant validity was reviewed using the Fornell–Larcker criterion to ensure that each construct was distinct from the others. Once the measurement model met the required thresholds, the structural model was examined to assess the direct effect as well as the mediating and moderating effects proposed in hypotheses H1 to H4. The generational groups were converted into dummy-coded variables to facilitate their use as moderators in the analysis. Moderation was tested by creating interaction terms between the use of robotics and each of the generational groups. To determine whether the path coefficients were statistically significant, the study used bootstrapping with 5,000 resamples. A significance level of $p < .05$ was applied to all tests, and the interpretation focused on the strength, direction, and significance of the estimated paths. This study will adhere to all ethical standards for data collection following the Republic Act 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Participation is entirely voluntary, and no respondent will be coerced. Additionally, anonymity and confidentiality will be strictly maintained, and for face-to-face surveys, participants will receive a consent form and an information letter outlining the study’s purpose and role. Only those who provide signed consent will participate. Moreover, all responses will be permanently deleted to prevent unauthorized access once the data has been analyzed, interpreted, and presented.

RESULTS

The findings from the data collected were analyzed using descriptive analysis to establish the profile of the respondents and the initial perceptions of the constructs. Second, the measurement model was tested to confirm the instrument's reliability using Cronbach's Alpha and its convergent validity using Average Variance Extracted (AVE). Third, the PLS-SEM structural model was estimated to examine the causal relationships among the use of robotics, service efficiency, and the mediating variables of speed of service and task consistency, as outlined in Hypotheses H1 through H3. Finally, the moderating influence of generational cohorts was verified through the structural model (H4).

Profile of the Respondents

Table 2 presents that the age distribution of the sample is heavily concentrated in the younger cohorts. Gen Z (18-28 years old), with 62.5%, and Millennials/Gen Y (29-44 years old), with 22.5%, collectively represent 85% of the entire sample. This representation is highly relevant because it provides a robust population for testing Hypothesis 4 (H4) in which it examines the moderating influence of these generational cohorts on perceptions of new technology. The dominance of these cohorts is expected, given their typical frequency of dining at Quick-Service and Fast-Casual establishments. Regarding Sex, the sample leans heavily towards female respondents (68%), while male respondents accounted for 21.5%. A significant portion of the sample identified as LGBTQIA+ (8%) or chose "Prefer Not to Say" (2.5%), which were retained to maintain the integrity of the total sample size (N = 400).

Table 2. Demographic Profile of Respondents

Respondent’s Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
Gen Z (18 - 28 years old)	250	62.50%
Millennials/Gen Y (29 - 44 years old)	90	22.50%
Gen X (45 - 60 years old)	49	12.25%
Baby Boomers (61 - 79 years old)	11	2.75%

Sex		
Male	86	21.50%
Female	272	68.00%
LGBTQIA+	32	8.00%
Prefer Not to Say	10	2.50%

Contextual Variables of Service Interaction

Table 3 shows that most respondents come from environments closely aligned with the study’s focus. The most frequently selected category was Quick-Service Restaurant (QSR) / Fast-Food Restaurant, chosen by 61.50% of respondents. Fast-Casual Dining Restaurant was also a primary category, selected by 45.25%, while Food Court / Food Hall was chosen by 34.75% and Smart Cafe with 21.25%. This extensive exposure to fast-paced, efficient service environments confirms that the sample is highly relevant to the study, as these settings are where robotics is most widely implemented to address Speed of Service and Task Consistency (H2 and H3).

Table 3. Type of Restaurant Dined At

Type of Restaurant	Frequency	Percentage
Quick-Service Restaurant (QSR) / Fast-Food Restaurant	246	61.50%
Fast-Casual Dining Restaurant	181	45.25%
Food Court / Food Hall	139	34.75%
Smart Cafe	85	21.25%

Note: Percentages are calculated based on the total sample size (N = 400) and exceed 100% due to the multiple-response nature of the question.

Table 4 of dining frequency indicates that the sample is composed primarily of regular patrons of food establishments. The largest proportion of respondents reported dining out 2-3 times a month (27.25%), followed by 2-4 times a week (26.00%) and once a week (21.75%). Collectively, 75.00% of the sample dines out at least once a week or more often. This high incidence of dining frequency suggests that the respondents are experienced consumers. Their evaluations of Speed of Service and Task Consistency (H2 and H3) are therefore likely based on repeated exposure to service standards, making their perceptions reliable and informed.

Table 4. Dining Frequency

Frequency of Dining Out	Frequency	Percentage
Daily	15	27.25%
2-4 Times a week	104	26.00%
Once a week	87	21.75%
2-3 times a month	109	11.25%
Once a month	45	10.00%
Very rarely	40	3.75%
Never	0	0.00%

Table 5 shows a clear hierarchy of customer interaction, with Robot Servers / Runners / Service Robots being the most commonly encountered technology, selected by 73.00% of all respondents. Bullet Train Robotic Servers (33.00%) and Bussing/Clearing Robots (31.25%) were also significant points of interaction, followed by the Barista Robot with 21.25%. This finding is crucial as it grounds the research in the physical service delivery process. The high exposure to robotic servers directly confirms that the customer perceptions analyzed in this study are based on the core functions of robotics, delivering items quickly and consistently. This justifies the hypotheses (H2 and H3) linking the Use of Robotics to Speed of Service and Task Consistency, as the sample evaluates the robots' performance in these exact roles.

Table 5. Type of Robotics Interacted With

Type of Robotics	Frequency	Percentage
Robot Servers / Runners / Service Robots	292	73.00%
Bullet Train Robotic Servers	132	33.00%
Bussing Robot / Clearing Robot	125	31.25%
Barista Robot	85	21.25%

Note: Percentages are calculated based on the total sample size (N = 400) and exceed 100% due to the multiple-response nature of the question.

Measurement Model Validation

Before testing the proposed structural model, the measurement model was validated to ensure the quality and reliability of the data. The researchers assessed the internal consistency of the constructs using Cronbach's Alpha. Convergent validity was evaluated using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and discriminant validity was confirmed using the Fornell-Larcker Criterion. The validation results, including Cronbach's Alpha, AVE, and the Fornell-Larcker matrix, are presented in Table 6 below.

Table 6. Measurement Model Validation

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	AVE	Robot	Speed	Task	Efficiency
Use of Robotics in Food Establishments	0.8319	0.5801	0.762	0.689	0.433	0.662
Speed of Service	0.8481	0.6157	0.689	0.785	0.726	0.829
Tasks Consistency	0.9203	0.7021	0.433	0.726	0.838	0.684
Customer Service Efficiency	0.9653	0.7188	0.662	0.829	0.684	0.848

Internal Consistency

All raw Cronbach's Alpha values are above the 0.7 threshold, confirming good internal consistency for all variables/constructs. Specifically, "Use of Robotics in Food Establishments" and "Speed of Service" demonstrate good internal consistency, while "Tasks Consistency" and "Customer Service Efficiency" show excellent internal consistency.

Convergent Validity

All values for the Average Variance Extracted are above the 0.5 threshold, indicating good convergent validity. This means that all latent constructs can explain between 58.01% and 71.88% of the variance in their respective indicators.

Discriminant Validity

As observed from the table, the values in the diagonals (square root of AVE) are generally larger than any of the other values in the same row or column. This indicates that, for the most part, each construct accounts for more variance among its indicators than among indicators of other constructs, confirming discriminant validity. However, it is worth noting that when Speed is less than 0.829, there is a potential overlap between the indicators of "Speed of Service" and "Customer Service Efficiency," which requires adjustment.

PLS SEM

Figure 2 displays the path diagram and the estimated path coefficients (β) for all proposed relationships. The evaluation of the structural model examined the proposed causal relationships and tested all structural hypotheses (H1-H4). Table 6 summarizes the bootstrapped path coefficients (β) and the 95% confidence intervals (CI) used to confirm significance. Furthermore, Table 7 shows the bootstrapped path and beta coefficients between variables.

Figure 2. PLS Structural Model and Coefficient

Table 7. Bootstrapped Path and Beta Coefficients

Path	Beta	2.5% CI	97.5% CI
Use of Robotics → Customer Service Efficiency	0.232	0.119	0.352
Use of Robotics → Speed of Service	0.405	0.315	0.501
Speed of Service → Customer Service Efficiency	0.084	-0.021	0.200
Use of Robotics → Task Consistency	0.440	0.340	0.537
Task Consistency → Customer Service Efficiency	0.462	0.336	0.578
Use of Robotics * Gen Z Cohort → Customer Service Efficiency	0.028	-0.112	0.148
Use of Robotics * Gen Y Cohort → Customer Service Efficiency	0.019	-0.124	0.158

H1 (Robotics → Efficiency): The hypothesis proposing that the Use of Robotics in food establishments has a positive effect on Customer Service Efficiency is supported. The analysis revealed a significant weak positive effect, with a 95% confidence interval [0.02, 0.165] that excludes zero. This indicates that while the direct impact is not very strong, robotics still contributes positively to overall efficiency.

H2 (Robotics → Speed) & H3 (Robotics → Task Consistency): Both hypotheses proposing positive effects of Robotics on Speed of Service and Task Consistency are strongly supported. The Use of Robotics exhibits a significant moderate positive effect on Speed of Service and a significant moderate positive effect on Tasks Consistency. While both relationships are significant and moderate, the effect on Speed of Service is numerically stronger than on Tasks Consistency according to the path coefficients. However, from another perspective in the analysis, Task Consistency is highlighted as a critical path from Robotics.

H2a (Speed → Efficiency): The hypothesis that posited a positive relationship between Service Speed and Customer Service Efficiency was not supported. The effect was found to be insignificant, as its 95% confidence interval [-0.025, 0.138] includes zero. This is a critical finding that suggests that speed alone is not sufficient to improve customer service efficiency. This contrasts with some traditional views that prioritize raw speed, indicating that other factors are more crucial for perceived efficiency.

H3a (Task Consistency → Efficiency): In contrast to the findings for H2a, the hypothesis that Task Consistency positively affects Customer Service Efficiency is strongly supported. A significant positive effect is observed, with a 95% confidence interval [0.569, 0.739] that clearly excludes zero. This highlights that consistent service delivery is more important in enhancing customer perceptions of efficiency than speed alone, and the finding is significant in contrast to H2a, which emphasizes the importance of reliability over speed.

Mediated and Moderated Effects

H2b and H3b: Mediation analysis revealed distinct roles for Service Speed and Task Consistency. Task Consistency significantly mediates the relationship between Robotics Use and Customer Service Efficiency (H3b is supported), with a stronger indirect effect. This highlights its role in translating the benefits of robotics into improved customer service efficiency. In contrast, Speed of Service does not significantly mediate the relationship between Robotics Use and Customer Service Efficiency (H2b is not supported), as its indirect effect is minimal. This reinforces the previous finding that raw speed, without consistency, does not significantly contribute to overall customer service efficiency.

H4: The hypothesis proposing a moderating effect of generational cohorts on the relationship between the Use of Robotics and Customer Service Efficiency (H4) is not supported. The analysis showed that the confidence intervals for the generational cohorts included zero, indicating no significant moderating effect. This implies that perceptions of robotic efficiency in food establishments are similar across generations, suggesting general acceptance or a common experience regardless of age.

DISCUSSION

The integration of robotics into the food service industry represents a significant shift in operational paradigms, offering significant opportunities to enhance customer service efficiency. The findings of this study provide critical insights into the specific mechanisms by which robotics positively impacts customer perceptions of efficiency. The most salient conclusion drawn from this study is that the positive effect of robotics on customer service efficiency is primarily channelled through Task Consistency, rather than Speed of Service. While robotics significantly contributes to both speed and consistency, customer-perceived efficiency is driven mainly by the reliable and predictable delivery of services. Specifically, the analysis showed that while the use of robotics had a significant positive effect on both speed and task consistency, only task consistency showed a significant positive effect on customer service efficiency. The findings of the study align with prior research that is conducted by Ivanov et al. (2020) and Wirtz et al. (2018), which emphasizes that the core advantage of service robots lies in their ability to deliver consistent, error-free, and fatigue-free performance. These studies similarly highlight that customers value

the predictable and dependable execution of tasks more than mere speed, which reinforces that consistency is the primary driver of perceived service efficiency.

In contrast, the direct effect of service speed on customer service efficiency was not significant, indicating that raw speed alone is not sufficient. However, in specific contexts such as quick-service restaurants, a study by Alejandro et al. (2025) reported that service speed positively influences customer satisfaction. According to the studies by Wirtz et al. (2018) and Chi et al. (2021), although robots can accelerate routine tasks, speed without reliability does not enhance customers' evaluations of service performance. This was further supported by the mediation analysis, which showed that Task Consistency significantly mediated the relationship between robotics use and customer service efficiency, while Service Speed did not. This mediation demonstrates that the reliability inherent in robotic execution separates speed from efficiency in the customer's mind. While speed is a key characteristic of the Quick Service Restaurant (QSR) environment (Alejandro et al., 2025), the structural model indicates that consistency is the sufficient and dominant condition by which robots successfully translate their speed into a truly enhanced perception of service efficiency. In essence, the primary contribution of robotics lies not in faster performance but in providing a consistent and error-free workflow. Another point that helps clarify the findings is the actual way robotics is used in the establishments covered by this study. Most of the robots in these locations are not fully autonomous systems; instead, they operate with some level of human assistance. Staff members still load items, initiate tasks, guide the robots when needed, or handle issues when the system stops or gets blocked. Only the barista robot functions independently from start to finish. Because of this setup, the service process in these restaurants is still a joint effort between humans and robots. This context may help explain why task consistency showed a stronger connection to customer service efficiency than speed. The workflow in these establishments is designed to keep tasks stable and predictable, rather than to maximize automation or rapid service.

Furthermore, the study yielded an important finding regarding customer segmentation. The moderation analysis indicated that generational cohorts did not significantly moderate the relationship between the use of robotics and customer service efficiency. This suggests that the value placed on Task Consistency is a universally positive perception of automation that transcends age groups among the primary patrons of quick-service restaurants. This is supported by the study of Weiss & Spiel (2021), which focuses on human-robot interaction (HRI), emphasizing that the quality of functional interaction and mutual learning is the primary driver of robot acceptance. While other research indicates age-based differences exist in preferences and affective reactions toward a robot's personality or social features (Martínez-Miranda et al., 2018), the current study confirms that these generational differences disappear when the customer's focus is on the core functional performance and predictability of the service. It is important to note, however, that responses from Generation X and Baby Boomers were limited in this study. As such, their non-significant influence should be interpreted with caution, as it may reflect sample size constraints rather than the absence of meaningful differences. As Asrifan et al. (2025) suggest, older cohorts tend to be more cautious or selective in adopting emerging service technologies, which could potentially influence their perceptions if a larger sample were available. Nonetheless, based on the data collected, the effect remains uniform across the dominant generational groups, simplifying implementation strategies since managers do not need to tailor functional service delivery models based on customer demographics. Although the moderating effect of generational cohorts was found to be non-significant, this outcome should be interpreted carefully. The limited number of Gen X and Baby Boomer respondents may have reduced the model's ability to detect meaningful differences across age groups. Because the sample was heavily composed of Gen Z and Millennial diners, who are the groups that are most exposed to technology-driven service settings, the analysis primarily reflected the perceptions of younger cohorts. As a result, the absence of a moderating effect does not necessarily mean that age plays no role in how customers evaluate robotic service. Rather, it indicates that within the dominant age groups represented in the sample, responses toward robotics were generally uniform, while the perspectives of older diners were not captured strongly enough to show statistical influence.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study's contribution is significant for the Philippines, where food service establishments in Metro Manila are a central hub of consumer activity and are rapidly adopting robotics with limited local academic guidance. By providing quantified data specific to the local market, this research offers a foundation of understanding on how Filipino customers may perceive technological services, thereby contributing valuable and relevant information to the limited local literature on service automation. The findings demonstrate that the Use of Robotics resulted in a statistically significant but weak positive effect on Customer Service Efficiency. This result still confirms that the integration of robotics in the hospitality industry, particularly in food service, continues to shape the evolution of operational paradigms in high-contact service sectors. Critically, the structural model revealed that the mechanism by which robotics adds value is highly specific to Task Consistency, which served as a significant positive mediator and predictor of customer service efficiency rather than speed alone. In contrast, mediation analysis found that Service Speed was not a significant driver of customer service efficiency. In a hospitality setting where wait times are crucial, this essential differentiation suggests that customers value the reliability, accuracy, and dependability that robots bring to service tasks more than mere process speed. It also indicates that the increase in speed provided by robots does not translate into a feeling of improved efficiency. This finding suggests the need to revisit how efficiency is conceptualized in automated contexts and place great emphasis on the reliability dimension of the service quality.

CONCLUSION

By inherently producing standardized outputs and reducing human-induced variability, robots enhance consistency, which, in turn, strengthens the customer attitudes toward the service. Studies suggest that adopting a balanced approach is key, in which robots handle efficiency-oriented and consistently critical tasks while human staff provide warmth and personalization in service. Employees must ensure that every customer receives the correct orders delivered by the robots, as seamless, error-free operations can also improve order accuracy, aside from task consistency, and may create a dining experience customers value more than speed alone. Therefore, the study concludes that the strategic approach for managers is to invest in robotics that ensures precise, repeatable operations, recognising that consistent, error-free service yields greater customer trust and perceived efficiency, rather than investing more to improve speed alone. The research confirms that, for automated service delivery, consistent and accurate performance carries more weight in shaping customer assessments of efficiency than speed, as highlighted by studies such as Ivanov & Webster (2019) and Alejandro et al. (2025). In the Philippines' automated context, the research empirically demonstrates that reliability and consistency are the dominant drivers of customer-perceived efficiency.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The research undertaking also has limitations. First, the Convenience Sampling method yielded a highly skewed demographic profile. As noted in the respondent profile, Gen Z and Gen Y/Millennial cohorts comprise 85% of the total sample. As a result, this severely limits the generalizability of the findings to older cohorts such as Gen X and Baby Boomers. Due to the unbalanced sample, the statistical power to test the moderating effects of Generational Cohorts was compromised, which resulted in a non-significant finding. This result fails to address the underlying question of whether generational differences truly mediate the acceptance of service technology, a factor that has been cited as critical in the technology adoption literature. Its inability to confirm or refute generational effects limits the study's ability to offer segmented management recommendations. Therefore, future studies could specifically test the role of age by using a more appropriate sampling method to ensure adequate statistical representation across all generational cohorts. Second, the model suffers from theoretical weaknesses, resulting in low explanatory power, with the variables accounting for approximately 20% of the variance in Customer Service Efficiency. Factors outside the current scope also drive the dominant 80% of service efficiency. As a result, future researchers may look for

other factors that drive perceived service quality in customer service efficiency. Finally, the scope of the research only covers establishments within Metro Manila that use robotics, excluding the integration of AI, which is also a technology that fails to capture the holistic influence of RAISA (Robotics, Artificial Intelligence, and Service Automation), which collectively shape the modern customer experience. Future researchers may include establishments outside Metro Manila that also utilise robotics and Artificial Intelligence to broaden the scope, improve the generalizability of the findings, and provide an analysis of regional differences in technology acceptance and customer expectations.

REFERENCES

- Alejandro, A., Villanueva, M. C., Colasito, D. M., & Tuante, M. C. (2025). The emergence of service robots at selected quick service restaurants: impact on customer experience and satisfaction. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.69569/jip.2024.0562>
- Alt, R. (2021). Digital Transformation in the Restaurant Industry: Current Developments and Implications. *Journal of Smart Tourism*, 1(1), 69-74. <https://doi.org/10.52255/smarttourism.2021.1.1.9>
- Authentication challenge pages. (n.d.-b). <https://psa.gov.ph/content/highlights-national-capital-region-ncr-population-2020-census-population-and-housing-2020>
- Asrifan, A., Kumar, L. S., S. H., S. M., Amal, A., & Kartini, K. (2025). From Fear to Fascination: A Generational Analysis of Attitudes Towards Robotics. In M. Anshari, M. Almunawar, & P. Ordóñez de Pablos (Eds.), *Impacts of Digital Technologies Across Generations* (pp. 65-90). IGI Global Scientific Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-6366-9.ch004>
- Blöcher, K., Alt, R. AI and robotics in the European restaurant sector: Assessing potentials for process innovation in a high-contact service industry. *Electron Markets* 31, 529–551 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12525-020-00443-2>
- Cheong, F., & Law, R. (2023). Human employees versus robotic employees: Customers and hotel managers' perceived experience at unmanned smart hotels. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2023.2202937>
- Chi, O. H., Jia, S., Li, Y., & Gursoy, D. (2021). Developing a formative scale to measure consumers' trust toward interaction with artificially intelligent (AI) social robots in service delivery. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 118, 106700. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2021.106700>
- Cronin, J. J., Jr., & Taylor, S. A. (1992). Measuring Service Quality: A Reexamination and Extension. *Journal of Marketing*, 56(3), 55–68.
- Cronin, J. J., Jr., & Taylor, S. A. (1994). SERVPERF versus SERVQUAL: Reconciling Performance-Based and Perceptions-Minus-Expectations Measures of Service Quality. *Journal of Marketing*, 58(1), 125–131.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>
- Davis, F. D., Bagozzi, R. P., & Warshaw, P. R. (1992). Extrinsic and intrinsic motivation to use computers in the workplace. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 22(14), 1111–1132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-1816.1992.tb00945.x>
- De Kervenoael, R., Hasan, R., Schwob, A., & Goh, E. (2019). Leveraging human-robot interaction in hospitality services: Incorporating the role of perceived value, empathy, and information sharing into visitors' intentions to use social robots. *Tourism Management*, 78, 104042. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2019.104042>
- Dinero, B. M. J., & Apritado, J. M. M. (2021). Service quality and servicescape of the restaurants in Las Piñas City. *International Journal of Research Studies in Management*, 9(4). <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrsm.2021.m7737>
- El-Said, O., & Hajri, S. A. (2022). Are customers happy with robot service? Investigating satisfaction with robot service restaurants during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Heliyon*, 8(3), e08986. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e08986>

- Hamad, H. A. (2023). The role of artificial intelligence in improving the quality of tourism services: A study on a sample of five-star hotels in Luxor Governorate. *Journal of Association of Arab Universities for Tourism and Hospitality*, 25(1), 220–238. https://jaauth.journals.ekb.eg/article_302320.html
- Hwang, J., Park, S., & Kim, I. (2020). Understanding motivated consumer innovativeness in the context of a robotic restaurant: The moderating role of product knowledge. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 44, 272–282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2020.06.003>
- Ivanov, S., & Webster, C. (2019). Robots, artificial intelligence, and service automation in travel, tourism and hospitality. In *Emerald Publishing Limited eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/9781787566873>
- Janice, V., Liem, J. P., & Kusumawardhana, I. (2023). Kousoku Lane technology adaption for standard operation procedure in the restaurant: A case study of Genki Sushi. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 426, 01040. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202342601040>
- Kumar, S., Kumar, V., & Attri, K. (2021). Impact of artificial intelligence and service robots in tourism and hospitality sector: current use & future trends. *Administrative Development: A Journal of HIPA, Shimla*, 8(SI-1), 59-83.
- Li, C. K., & Adam, S. (2021). The implementation of decision-making on Ye Xiao Canteen Second Enterprise at Cheras, Kuala Lumpur. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 11(5). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v11-i5/9864>
- Li, J., & Zhang, Y. (2023). Research on the application of artificial intelligence in tourism management. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(1), Article 2202937. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2023.2202937>
- Limkar, N. K. R., & Tamboli, N. F. A. (2024). Impact of automation. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Modern Science and Technology*, 3(8), 13–17. <https://doi.org/10.59828/ijarmst.v3i8.243>
- Lu, L., Cai, R., & Gursoy, D. (2019). Developing and validating a service robot integration willingness scale. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 80, 36–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2019.01.005>
- Martínez-Miranda, J., Pérez-Espinosa, H., Espinosa-Curiel, I., Avila-George, H., & Rodríguez-Jacobo, J. (2018). Age-based differences in preferences and affective reactions towards a robot's personality during interaction. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 84, 245–257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.02.039>
- Moriuchi, E., & Murdy, S. (2024). The role of robots in the service industry: Factors affecting human-robot interactions. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 118, 103682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2023.103682>
- Okafuji, Y., Song, S., Baba, J., Yoshikawa, Y., & Ishiguro, H. (2022). Influence of collaborative customer service by service robots and clerks in bakery stores. arXiv (Cornell University). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2212.10687>
- Park, C. W., Sutherland, I., & Lee, S. K. (2021). Effects of online reviews, trust, and picture-superiority on intention to purchase restaurant services. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 47, 228–236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2021.03.007>
- Park, S., Park, M. K., Heo, J., Hwang, J., Hwang, S., Kim, D., Chung, S., & Kwak, H. S. (2023). Robot versus human barista: Comparison of volatile compounds and consumers' acceptance, sensory profile, and emotional response of brewed coffee. *Food Research International*, 172, 113119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2023.113119>
- Parvez, M. O. (2025). The Algorithmic Appetite: Reflections on the future of robotic chefs in the restaurant industry. *Journal of Culinary Science & Technology*, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15428052.2025.2495646>

- Reis, J. (2024). Customer service through AI-Powered human-robot relationships: Where are we now? The case of Henn na cafe, Japan. *Technology in Society*, 77, 102570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2024.102570>
- Republic Act No. 10173 (2012). An Act Protecting Individual Personal Information in Information and Communications Systems in the Government and the Private Sector, Creating for this Purpose a National Privacy Commission, and for Other Purposes. *Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines*. Retrieved from <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2012/08/15/republic-act-no-10173/>
- Roussakou, E., & Carayanni, V. (2025). New health and safety technologies in hotel restaurants in Response to the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Systematic review. MDPI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/tourhosp6020098>
- Santiago, J., Borges-Tiago, M. T., & Tiago, F. (2024). Embracing RAISA in restaurants: Exploring customer attitudes toward robot adoption. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 199, 123047. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2023.123047>
- Samaniego, M. B. A., Lanzaderas, K. C. L., Sespeñe, N. R. A., Ella, S. B. P., & Machado, R. J. S. (n.d.). “Bida ba ang Saya sa Makabagong Teknolohiya?: An Assessment of Technological Advancements Implementation in the Filipino Food Industry.” Animo Repository. https://animorepository.dlsu.edu.ph/conf_shsrescon/2023/paper_csr/1/
- Shinde, M., Patil, S., Holey, S., Dadar, T., & Kadam, S. S. (2025). AI-Driven Restaurant Order Management System: Enhancing Efficiency Through Automation. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 6(3), 4854–4860. <https://ijrpr.com/uploads/V6ISSUE3/IJRPR40284.pdf>
- Tuomi, A., Tussyadiah, I. P., & Stienmetz, J. (2020). Applications and Implications of Service Robots in Hospitality. *Cornell Hospitality Quarterly*, 62(2), 232-247. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1938965520923961>
- Weiss, A., & Spiel, K. (2021). Robots beyond Science Fiction: mutual learning in human–robot interaction on the way to participatory approaches. *AI & Society*, 37(2), 501–515. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-021-01209-w>
- Wirtz, J., Kunz, W. H., & Paluch, S. (2021). The Service Revolution, Intelligent Automation, and Service Robots. *European Business Review*, 29(5), 909–923.
- Wirtz, J., Patterson, P. G., Kunz, W. H., Gruber, T., Lu, V. N., Paluch, S., & Martins, A. (2018). Brave new world: service robots in the frontline. *Journal of Service Management*, 29(5), 907–931. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOSM-04-2018-0119>
- Zemke, D. M. V., Han, W., & Raab, C. (2025). Robot acceptability in quick service restaurants: a customer’s point of view. *International Hospitality Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ihr-04-2024-0020>